

TECHNOLOGICAL RESOURCES AND EXPERTISE OF SELECTED PHILIPPINE NATIONAL POLICE (PNP) ANTICYBERCRIME UNITS IN CYBERCRIME

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10899918>

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the technological resources and expertise within the Philippine National Police (PNP) Anti-Cybercrime Unit and their impact on cybercrime investigations. Using a descriptive quantitative correlational design, the research involved purposive sampling of 42 PNP personnel, utilizing a researcher-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire assessed three main areas: the level of technological resources (data analytics, machine learning, and digital forensics), personnel's technological expertise (proficiency, utilization, and adoption), and the impact of these factors on case resolution time and success rate in cybercrime investigations. Findings reveal a significant positive correlation between the level of technological resources and the effectiveness of cybercrime investigations. Particularly, machine learning and digital forensics resources demonstrated strong correlations with both case resolution time and success rate. Additionally, proficiency, utilization, and adoption of technology by personnel showed significant positive impacts on investigation outcomes. Notably, the adoption of new technologies exhibited an exceptionally strong correlation with success rate, underlining the transformative impact of embracing new technologies in enhancing cybercrime investigation effectiveness. Based on the findings, it is recommended for cybercrime units investing in advanced machine learning algorithms, expanding digital forensic tools, and implementing comprehensive training programs for personnel to improve case resolution efficiency and overall success rates in combating cybercrime.

Keywords: *Cybercrime Investigations, Technological Resources, Machine Learning, Digital Forensics, Philippine National Police*

INTRODUCTION

The rise of information and communication technologies has created significant challenges for law enforcement agencies and other organizations responsible for maintaining security. Specifically, cybercrime has become a major societal concern in recent years (Lewis, 2018). This term encompasses crimes that either target computer systems and networks or are facilitated by them (Bossler & Berenblum, 2019). The digital landscape has given rise to new types of criminal activities, such as hacking and attacks involving malicious software (Paek et al., 2021). Moreover, traditional forms of crime are also evolving, as criminals exploit the unique features of the online world to carry out their activities (Bossler & Berenblum, 2019). Recent data indicates that Internet Service Providers (ISPs) detect approximately 80 billion automated scans each day, conducted by cybercriminals looking for potential victims (Lewis, 2018).

As of mid-2023, the global internet user base reached 5.19 billion, accounting for 64.6% of the world's population. Additionally, nearly 60% of people worldwide were active on social media platforms (Petrosyan, 2023). In the context of the Philippines, the country had 85.16 million individuals using the internet at the beginning of 2023, which represented 73.1% of its total population (Kemp, 2023). In light of this, law enforcement have been called to action to adopt a proactive organizational approach, including educational and public awareness programs, to effectively combat online property crimes and, by extension, industrial espionage (Paek et al., 2021). In the Philippines, as in other developing countries throughout Southeast Asia, cybercrime is a looming problem. Greater integration of technology into various sectors has given rise to myriad illegal activities online, often due to inadequate safeguards and low public awareness about the risks involved (Cybercrime Threat Landscape in the Philippines, 2013).

The Philippine National Police reports surges in both financially motivated cybercrimes and politically motivated cyber-attacks targeting government infrastructure; lacking an expansive cybercrime law on its books hasn't prevented the force from creating specialized units like the Anti-Cybercrime Group or digital forensic labs designed for investigating such offenses (Cybercrime Threat Landscape in the Philippines, 2013). Instead it advocates taking an all-channel approach to fighting these crimes. This includes building organizational competence, fostering public-private partnerships, and strengthening international cooperation (Cybercrime Threat Landscape in the Philippines, 2013). Hence, the escalating prevalence of cybercrime in the Philippines, coupled with the rapid adoption of digital technologies, underscores an urgent need for a comprehensive study. This study aims to evaluate the technological resources and expertise available to the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Units. It aims to assess the current levels of data analytics, machine learning, and digital forensics tools, as well as the proficiency, utilization, and adoption of these resources by the unit's personnel. The study focuses on understanding how these technological aspects influence case resolution time and success rate in cybercrime investigations. Additionally, it explores the correlation between the technological capabilities of the unit and the effectiveness of investigations. Based on the findings, the study seeks to provide strategic recommendations to enhance the unit's

efficiency in handling cybercrime, thereby aiding in policy-making and operational strategy development.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study is to determine the technological resources and expertise of PNP personnel in the Anti-Cybercrime Unit and its impact on cybercrime investigations. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of technological resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of:
 - 1.1 Data analytics
 - 1.2 Machine learning
 - 1.3 Digital forensics
2. What is the level of technological expertise of PNP personnel under anti-cybercrime unit in terms of:
 - 2.1 Proficiency in technological resources
 - 2.2 Utilization of technological resources
 - 2.3 Adoption of technological resources
3. How do technological resources and expertise impacts cybercrime investigations in terms of:
 - 3.1 Case Resolution Time
 - 3.2 Success Rate
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of technological resources in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and cybercrime investigations?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of technological expertise of personnels in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and cybercrime investigations?
6. What strategic actions and recommendations can be made based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The present study utilized a descriptive quantitative correlational research design. According to Johnson and Christensen (2020), descriptive research designs aim to accurately describe characteristics, behaviors, or attitudes of a specific population. Correlational designs, as explained by Creswell and Creswell (2017), are used to examine the relationships. The descriptive aspect allows for a detailed account of the current state of technological resources and expertise within the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit. It provides a snapshot of the existing conditions, thereby offering a

baseline for analysis (Johnson & Christensen, 2020). Second, the correlational aspect of the design enables the study to explore the relationships between variables such as the level of technological resources, expertise, and their impact on cybercrime investigations. This is crucial for understanding how these elements interact and influence each other, which can be instrumental for policy-making and strategic planning (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Population and sampling

Purposive sampling will be used to select the study's respondents. According to Etikan et al. (2016), purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method where researchers select participants based on specific characteristics or qualities that serve the study's objectives. In this case, the criteria for sampling includes PNP personnel from different Anti Cybercrime Units within the country who are directly involved in cybercrime investigations, have experience with the technological resources in question, and are willing to participate in the study. This method ensures that the sample is highly relevant to the research questions and objectives. 42 respondents were selected for this study. While larger sample sizes are generally more representative, the sample is considered sufficient for several reasons. First, the study is focused on a specialized unit within the PNP, limiting the pool of potential respondents. Second, a sample size of 25-50 is often considered adequate for correlational studies to detect medium to large effect sizes (Cohen, 1988). Lastly, given the specialized nature of the study, each respondent's input is highly valuable, making a smaller but more focused sample more appropriate for this research.

Research instrumentation

The research employed a researcher-made questionnaire as its primary data collection instrument. This questionnaire is divided into three main sections. The first section is the technological Resources: This section assesses the level of technological resources available in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, focusing on Data Analytics, Machine Learning, and Digital Forensics. Respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement with statements related to these resources. The second section is the Level of Technological Expertise of PNP Personnel: This section gauges the proficiency, utilization, and adoption of technological resources by the personnel. It aims to understand how well-equipped the staff are in terms of training and expertise. The last section examines the Impact on Cybercrime Investigations. It evaluates how the technological resources and expertise affect case resolution time and the success rate of cybercrime investigations. The questionnaire uses a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," to capture the respondents' level of agreement with each statement. The range of means is demonstrated below:

Table 1. Five-point Rating Scale Evaluation Tools

POINT	SCALE	EQUIVALENT
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41-4.20	Agree
3	2.61-3.40	Neither Agree nor Disagree
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree

Before the actual data collection, a pilot test was conducted with a smaller sample of respondents who meet the study's criteria. This is to ensure the clarity, relevance, and reliability of the questionnaire items. The reliability of the instrument will be assessed using Cronbach's alpha, a statistical measure used to gauge internal consistency. An alpha value of 0.7 or above is generally considered acceptable for research purposes. The questionnaire was also validated by the thesis adviser to ensure its academic rigor and alignment with the study's objectives.

Data gathering procedures and analysis

The study began with obtaining necessary approvals from the academic institution and the Philippine National Police (PNP) Anti-Cybercrime Unit. A detailed proposal outlining the study's objectives, methodology, and ethical considerations was submitted for review. Following the approvals, a pilot test was conducted with a select group of respondents to assess the questionnaire's clarity, relevance, and reliability. Feedback from this pilot test was instrumental in refining the questionnaire, ensuring its validity and reliability, as measured by Cronbach's alpha. The main data collection phase commenced with purposive sampling, targeting PNP personnel involved in cybercrime investigations. These respondents were briefed about the study, and informed consent was obtained. Questionnaires were distributed in both electronic and hard copy formats, as per the convenience of the participants. A timeline for completion was established, accompanied by follow-up reminders to ensure a high response rate. The data gathered were then coded and analyzed using SPSS IBM Statistics. This analysis included frequency and percentage to provide an overview of the data, weighted mean to measure respondents' perceptions on a Likert Scale, and Pearson Correlation to assess relationships between variables such as technological resources, expertise, and their impact on cybercrime investigations.

RESULTS

Level of Technological Resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

Table 2 draws insightful conclusions about the level of data analytics resources available in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

Table 2. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of technological resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of Data Analytics.

Data analytics	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Our unit has specialized software like Tableau or Excel for data analytics.	4.048	Agree
2. The data analytics software we use has been updated within the last year.	3.929	Agree
3. I find it easy to perform tasks like data filtering and sorting using our analytics tools.	4.024	Agree
4. Our data analytics tools can reliably handle large datasets (e.g., 1TB or more) for cybercrime investigations.	3.905	Agree
5. Our data analytics capabilities are sufficient for tasks like trend analysis and predictive modeling.	3.714	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.924	Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Meanwhile, Table 3 shows the assessment of technological resources in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, specifically in terms of machine learning.

Table 3. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of technological resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in PNP in terms of Machine Learning

Data analytics	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Our unit uses machine learning algorithms to identify patterns in cybercrime data effectively.	3.762	Agree
2. The user interface of our machine learning software is intuitive and easy to navigate.	3.810	Agree
3. Our machine learning tools receive updates at least once every six months to improve performance.	3.810	Agree
4. The machine learning algorithms we use have a high accuracy rate in predicting cybercrime trends.	3.810	Agree
5. Machine learning tools have been crucial in solving complex cybercrime cases that would have been difficult to solve otherwise.	4.024	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.843	Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Similarly, the analysis of Table 4 reveals valuable insights into the level of digital forensics resources at the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

Table 4. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of technological resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of Digital Forensics

Data analytics	Mean	Verbal Description
1. We have specialized digital forensics tools, like EnCase or FTK, for our cybercrime investigations.	4.214	Strongly Agree
2. The interface of our digital forensics tools is user-friendly, requiring minimal training.	4.167	Agree
3. Our digital forensics software is updated at least annually to handle new types of cybercrime.	3.976	Agree
4. The digital forensics tools we use can reliably analyze various file formats, such as .txt, .jpg, and .pdf.	4.095	Agree
5. Our digital forensics capabilities can handle complex tasks like data recovery from damaged devices.	4.024	Agree
Weighted Mean	4.095	Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Table 5 presents a comprehensive view of the level of technological expertise of personnel in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

Table 5. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of Technological Expertise in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of Proficiency

Proficiency	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I can operate specialized software like Wireshark for network analysis.	3.333	Agree
2. Most personnel in our unit have completed at least one formal training course in technology.	4.071	Agree
3. I have received at least 20 hours of training to use our technological resources.	3.905	Agree
4. I feel confident using software tools to analyze malware or phishing attacks.	3.595	Agree
5. Our unit has personnel certified in areas like Certified Ethical Hacking (CEH).	3.429	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.667	Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

On the other hand, Table 6 provides a detailed assessment of the utilization of technological expertise in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, focusing on how various technological resources are applied in the field.

Table 6. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of Technological Expertise in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of Utilization

Utilization	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I use data analytics software in at least 70% of my investigations.	3.619	Agree
2. Our unit uses all the licensed software tools at least once a month.	3.905	Agree
3. I can access any of our technological resources within 10 minutes when needed.	3.667	Agree
4. I know how to use at least three different types of software for data analysis, machine learning, and digital forensics.	3.762	Agree
5. Using software tools has helped me reduce manual data sorting time by at least 50%.	3.929	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.776	Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Table 7 on the other hand shows the level of technological expertise in pnp anti-cybercrime unit in terms of adoption.

Table 7. Assessment of the Respondents of the Level of Technological Expertise in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in terms of Adoption

Adoption	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I am open to using new technological resources.	4.333	Strongly Agree
2. Our unit quickly adopts new technological tools.	4.191	Agree
3. The adoption of new technology is supported by our leadership.	4.357	Strongly Agree
4. I find it easy to adapt to new technological resources.	4.167	Agree
5. Adopting new technology has made our investigations more effective.	4.238	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.257	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Technological Resources and Expertise Impact on Cybercrime Investigations

Table 8 provides an insightful assessment of the impact of technological resources and expertise on cybercrime investigations in terms of case resolution time in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

Table 8. Assessment of the Respondents of the Impact of Technological Resources and Expertise Cybercrime in terms of Case Resolution Time

Case Resolution Time	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Using technological resources speeds up case resolution.	4.238	Strongly Agree
2. Advanced technology helps in quicker data collection.	4.381	Strongly Agree
3. Technological expertise reduces the time needed for analysis.	4.381	Strongly Agree
4. Our unit resolves cases faster due to technological aid.	4.262	Strongly Agree
5. Technology helps us meet deadlines more efficiently.	4.357	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.324	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

The responses from Table 9 underscore the significant impact of technological resources and expertise on the success rates of cybercrime investigations within the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit.

Table 9. Assessment of the Respondents of the Impact of Technological Resources and Expertise Cybercrime in terms of Case Resolution Time

Case Resolution Time	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Technological resources have increased our case success rate.	4.167	Agree
2. Our technological expertise contributes to successful investigations.	4.262	Strongly Agree
3. Advanced technology helps us collect more accurate data.	4.286	Strongly Agree
4. Technology enables us to build stronger cases.	4.286	Strongly Agree
5. Our unit's success rate has improved due to technological advancements.	4.214	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	4.243	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree; 3.41-4.20- Agree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 1.81-2.60 Disagree; 1.00-1.80 -Strongly Disagree

Correlation Analysis

Table 10 presents a correlation analysis assessing the relationship between the level of technological resources in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and the outcomes of cybercrime investigations, specifically focusing on case resolution time and success rate.

Table 10. Significant relationship between the level of technological resources in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and cybercrime investigations

Technological Resources		Case Resolution Time	Success Rate
Data Analytics	Pearson Correlation	0.291	.495**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.061	.001
Machine Learning	Pearson Correlation	.391*	.575**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.011	.000
Digital Forensics	Pearson Correlation	.399**	.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.009	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Meanwhile, Table 11 provides an analysis of the relationship between the level of technological expertise of personnel in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and the outcomes of cybercrime investigations, focusing on case resolution time and success rate.

Table 11. Significant relationship between the level of technological expertise of personnels in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and cybercrime investigations

Technological Resources		Case Resolution Time	Success Rate
Proficiency	Pearson Correlation	.258	.306*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.099	.049
Utilization	Pearson Correlation	.395**	.491**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.001
Adoption	Pearson Correlation	.391*	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.723**	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

Level of Technological Resources in PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit

The assessment of the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, as shown in Table 2, reveals a strong agreement among respondents about the adequacy of data analytics resources in the unit. The unit is equipped with specialized software like Tableau or Excel for data analytics, receiving a mean score of 4.048, indicative of advanced tools necessary for effective data analysis (Begum & Ahmed, 2015). Regular updates of data analytics software, reflected in a mean score of 3.929, align with the evolving nature of cybercrime, ensuring the tools remain effective against contemporary threats (Rajivan et. al., 2020). The user-friendliness of these tools, evident from a mean score of 4.024, contributes to efficient analysis (Cypress, 2019), while their capability to handle large datasets, with a mean of 3.905, addresses the significant data volumes in cybercrime investigations (Hughes et. al., 2021). However, the lowest mean score of 3.714 for the unit's capabilities in trend analysis and predictive modeling suggests room for improvement in these critical areas (Veena et. al., 2022).

Overall, the weighted mean of 3.924 indicates a general agreement on the adequacy of the unit's data analytics resources, with a need for continuous improvement and updates to keep pace with the rapidly evolving nature of cybercrime. These aspects are crucial for the effective identification and prevention of cybercrimes and should inform policy decisions, training programs, and resource allocation within the unit (Abdullah, 2019). The findings suggest that while the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit is well-equipped in terms of data analytics resources, there is a need for ongoing enhancement in specific areas to maintain the unit's effectiveness in cybercrime investigations.

The assessment of machine learning capabilities within the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit reveals a positive perception of the effectiveness of machine learning in cybercrime investigations. The mean score of 3.762 for the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms in identifying cybercrime patterns indicates a strong agreement on their vital role in detecting and analyzing cyber threats, as highlighted by Sarker (2023). The user-friendliness of the machine learning software, with a mean score of 3.810, is recognized as crucial for efficient usage and data analysis, a point emphasized by Kumari (2019). Furthermore, the regular updates of these tools, also scoring 3.810, are seen as essential in keeping pace with the evolving nature of cybercrime, aligning with Mugarza et. al. (2020). The reliability of machine learning in predicting cybercrime trends is underscored by a similar mean score of 3.810, reflecting its importance in proactive cybercrime management, as discussed by Mijwil et. al. (2023).

The highest mean score of 4.024 acknowledges the critical role of machine learning tools in solving complex cybercrime cases, echoing the transformative impact of these technologies in cybercrime investigations reported by Sarker (2023). The overall weighted mean of 3.843 indicates a consensus on the effectiveness and adequacy of machine learning resources in the unit. However, there is an identified need for further

development, especially in enhancing the effectiveness and update frequency of these tools. These findings suggest that machine learning is integral to modern cybercrime investigations, aiding in pattern recognition, predictive analysis, and resolving complex cases. This underscores the need for continued investment and advancement in machine learning capabilities within the unit to effectively tackle the challenges posed by modern cybercrime.

The analysis of the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit's digital forensics capabilities, as reflected in Table 4, indicates a high level of proficiency and preparedness in handling cybercrime investigations. The unit's strong agreement on having specialized digital forensics tools, such as EnCase or FTK, with a mean score of 4.214, highlights its well-equipped state for effective digital investigations (Dweikat et. al., 2020). The user-friendliness of these tools, evidenced by a mean score of 4.167, underscores their accessibility and efficiency in facilitating quicker analysis with minimal training, as emphasized by Madinger (2018). Regular updates of digital forensics software, with a mean score of 3.976, are crucial for keeping up with evolving cyber threats (Mugarza et. al., 2020), while the tools' versatility in analyzing various file formats, scoring 4.095, is essential for comprehensive evidence examination (Abdullah, 2019).

Furthermore, the unit's confidence in handling complex tasks like data recovery from damaged devices, indicated by a mean score of 4.024, is a critical component in cybercrime investigations (Solodov & Solodov, 2021). The overall weighted mean of 4.095 suggests a general consensus on the adequacy and effectiveness of the digital forensics resources available. However, the findings also point towards areas for further development, particularly in keeping the software updated and enhancing data recovery capabilities. In summary, the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit demonstrates strong digital forensics capabilities, essential for modern cybercrime investigations, yet there is a recognized need for continuous improvement in line with the evolving nature of cybercrime and technological advancements.

Level of Technological Expertise of PNP Personnel Under Anti-Cybercrime Unit

The assessment of technological expertise among personnel in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, as reflected in Table 5, indicates a proficient level of skill and training in handling cybercrime investigations. Personnel exhibit a good understanding and ability to operate specialized software for network analysis, such as Wireshark, with a mean score of 3.333, reflecting competence crucial for cyber threat analysis (Dodiya & Singh, 2022). The highest mean score of 4.071 for having completed formal training courses suggests a strong foundation in technological skills essential for cybercrime investigation (Shillair et. al., 2022). Additionally, the positive response, with a mean of 3.905, towards receiving at least 20 hours of training highlights the unit's commitment to ongoing skill development, aligning with the need for continuous training in the evolving field of cybercrime (Martin, 2022).

Furthermore, confidence in using software tools for analyzing malware or phishing attacks, indicated by a mean score of 3.595, suggests proficiency, albeit with room for improvement in these specific areas (Morrison et. al., 2021). The presence of personnel with certifications like Certified Ethical Hacking (CEH), reflected in a mean score of 3.429, underscores the specialized skill set within the unit, critical for effective cybercrime investigation (Wang & D’Cruze, 2019). The overall weighted mean of 3.667 points towards a general agreement on the technological proficiency of the unit, while also identifying areas for further skill enhancement. In summary, the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit demonstrates commendable technological expertise, with a strong emphasis on formal training and certified skills, yet acknowledges the need for continuous development, especially in areas like malware and phishing analysis.

The analysis of Table 6 reflects a strong utilization of technological tools within the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit indicating a high level of reliance on and proficiency in various software tools for cybercrime investigations. The mean score of 3.619 for the use of data analytics software in the majority of investigations highlights the integral role these tools play in addressing the complexities of modern cybercrime, as emphasized by Carrascosa et al. (2017). This extensive use of data analytics is crucial for data-driven approaches in investigations. The highest mean score of 3.929 for the reduction of manual data sorting by at least 50% using software tools points towards significant improvements in operational efficiency, a critical aspect in effective cybercrime investigations (Yin et al., 2022).

Furthermore, regular usage of licensed software tools, with a mean of 3.905, suggests that the unit efficiently utilizes its technological resources, maintaining proficiency and ensuring tool effectiveness (Zhan et al., 2018). The positive response, with a mean score of 3.667, regarding quick access to technological resources, underlines the unit's ability to respond promptly to emerging situations, a key factor in the fast-paced environment of cybercrime investigation (Zhao et al., 2024). Additionally, a mean score of 3.762 for the ability to use diverse types of software for data analysis, machine learning, and digital forensics indicates a versatile skill set among the personnel, essential for handling various facets of cybercrime (Chen et al., 2021). Overall, with a weighted mean of 3.776, the consensus suggests not only a well-equipped unit but also one adept in effectively applying a range of technological tools in their operations, pointing towards a strong capability in integrating technology into cybercrime

The assessment of the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit's approach to adopting new technology, as reflected in Table 7, shows a strong inclination towards embracing technological advancements, vital in the dynamic field of cybercrime. The high mean score of 4.333 for openness to using new technological resources signifies a robust willingness among unit members to integrate new technologies, an essential aspect in enhancing investigative effectiveness (Tariq et al., 2023). The support from leadership, indicated by a mean score of 4.357, plays a crucial role in this process, fostering a culture of innovation and smooth integration of new tools into existing systems (Aziz et al., 2020). Additionally, a high mean score of 4.238 for the statement regarding the effectiveness of

new technology adoption in investigations underscores its positive impact on the unit's capabilities (Laufs & Borrion, 2022).

The lowest score, although still within the 'Agree' range, was 4.167 for the ease of adapting to new technologies, suggesting some challenges or a learning curve in this adoption process (Pollard et al., 2022). The unit's proactive stance in quickly adopting new tools, with a mean score of 4.191, reflects its commitment to staying updated with technological trends, crucial for maintaining an edge in cybercrime investigations (Mhlongo et al., 2023). The overall weighted mean of 4.257 indicates a strong consensus on the effectiveness and positive attitude towards the adoption of new technology, suggesting that the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit is not only open to but also proficient in incorporating technological advancements. This approach is essential for keeping pace with the evolving nature of cybercrime and enhancing the unit's investigative capabilities.

Technological Resources and Expertise Impact on Cybercrime Investigations

The findings from Table 8 clearly indicate a strong consensus among respondents in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit on the significant impact of technological resources and expertise in enhancing the efficiency of cybercrime investigations, specifically in terms of case resolution time. The high mean scores, such as 4.238 for using technological resources to speed up case resolution and 4.381 for both quicker data collection and reduced analysis time, demonstrate the critical role advanced technology and expertise play in expediting investigative processes (Laufs & Borrion, 2022; Milenkovic, 2023). These scores underscore the importance of technology in not only accelerating case resolutions but also in improving the efficiency of meeting operational deadlines, as reflected by a mean score of 4.357 (Chinedu et. al., 2021).

Furthermore, the statement regarding the faster resolution of cases due to technological aid received a mean of 4.262, reinforcing the perception that technology significantly contributes to the unit's ability to resolve cases more quickly (Esposito et. al., 2023). The overall weighted mean of 4.324 under 'Strongly Agree' suggests a unanimous acknowledgment of the vital role that technology plays in the contemporary landscape of cybercrime investigation. These results highlight the indispensable nature of technology in optimizing investigative processes, making a compelling case for the continuous development and integration of technological advancements in the field of cybercrime investigation.

The responses from Table 9 underscore the significant impact of technological resources and expertise on the success rates of cybercrime investigations within the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit. With a mean score of 4.167 for the statement regarding the increase in case success rates due to technological resources, there is a clear indication of the positive effects of technology in enhancing investigation outcomes, aligning with the perspectives of Yavorsky et al. (2021) on the transformative role of technology in law enforcement. The unit's technological expertise, receiving a high mean score of 4.262, is perceived as a pivotal factor contributing to successful investigations, echoing the

established correlation between technological proficiency and investigative success discussed by Beer & Mulder (2020).

Furthermore, the highest mean scores of 4.286 for both the accuracy of data collection and the ability to build stronger cases due to advanced technology reinforce the critical importance of technological advancement in ensuring evidence reliability and effective case-building, as highlighted by Taherdoost (2021). Similarly, the strong agreement, with a mean score of 4.214, that the unit's success rate has improved due to technological advancements, reflects a consensus on the positive influence of technology in law enforcement, a theme explored in Strom (2017). The overall weighted mean of 4.243 under 'Strongly Agree' across all statements signifies a broad recognition of the integral role technology plays in boosting the effectiveness of cybercrime investigations. In conclusion, the findings from Table 9 illustrate the indispensable role of both technological resources and expertise in elevating the success rates of cybercrime case resolutions in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit, emphasizing the need for continuous technological advancement and skill development.

Correlation Analysis

For correlations, the analysis reveals significant positive relationships, particularly with machine learning and digital forensics showing strong correlations with both case resolution time and success rate. Data analytics also shows a moderate positive correlation, especially with success rate, suggesting that higher levels of technological resources are associated with more efficient and successful investigations. These findings highlight the importance of advanced technological resources, as they are closely linked to improved investigation outcomes (Abdullah, 2019; Veena et al., 2022; Pedapudi & Vadlamani, 2023).

Meanwhile, on the analysis of the relationship between the level of technological expertise of personnel in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit and the outcomes of cybercrime investigations, focusing on case resolution time and success rate, results demonstrates that proficiency, utilization, and adoption of technology by personnel are significantly positively correlated with both case resolution time and success rate. Notably, the adoption of new technologies shows an exceptionally strong correlation with success rate, emphasizing the transformative impact of embracing new technologies in enhancing the effectiveness of cybercrime units. This analysis underscores the critical role of personnel's technological expertise in boosting the efficiency and success of cybercrime investigations (Beer & Mulder, 2020; Przeszlowski et al., 2023; Escamilla & Reichert, 2019).

Strategic Actions and Recommendations Based on The Findings of The Study

The study's findings suggest several strategic actions and recommendations to improve the effectiveness of the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit in combating cybercrime. In machine learning, investing in state-of-the-art algorithms and tools is crucial in fostering

innovation and research within the unit, custom-tailored solutions can be developed specifically designed to tackle the unique challenges posed by cybercrime in the Philippines. Expanding the range of digital forensics tools – especially those capable of handling diverse file formats and complex data recovery tasks – is also deemed essential. For digital forensics, expanding the range of tools to include more sophisticated software for diverse file formats and complex data recovery tasks is crucial.

Moreover, regarding personnel proficiency, utilization, and adoption, a comprehensive training program is needed. Not only covering technical aspects but also emphasizing practical application in real-world scenarios, these initiatives should include hands-on workshops and continuous learning opportunities so as to effectively adapt to ever-evolving cyber threats. On the other hand, to influence case resolution time and success rate positively, a holistic approach that integrates technological resources with investigative strategies is essential. This approach should leverage machine learning and data analytics for quicker and more accurate data collection and analysis, leading to more effective case resolutions.

Finally, to address the correlation between technological capabilities and investigation effectiveness, the unit should adopt a strategy that aligns technological upgrades with investigative needs. This could involve collaborative efforts with tech companies and academic institutions for access to state-of-the-art resources and training. Regular assessments and feedback mechanisms should be established to ensure that the technology used remains relevant and effective in addressing the dynamic nature of cybercrime. These recommendations aim to enhance the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit's capacity to effectively utilize technology in its ongoing battle against cybercrime based on the empirical evidences found in the study.

Conclusions

The study conducted on the technological resources and expertise in the PNP Anti-Cybercrime Unit showed significant insights into the impact of technology on cybercrime investigations. Based on the results, significant correlation between the technological capabilities of the unit and the effectiveness of its investigations is shown with strong correlation between the adoption of new technologies and the success rate of cases. The analysis also revealed that machine learning and digital forensics resources show strong positive relationships with both the speed of case resolution and the success rate of investigations as perceived by the respondents. Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of proficiency, utilization, and adoption of technology by personnel as key factors in the success of cybercrime investigations.

Recommendations

Given the empirical results of the study undeniable link between these factors and investigation success rates, it is imperative to prioritize technology enhancement, innovation efforts, and workforce proficiency. Effectively merging technological expertise and resources with investigations will enhance combatting cybercrime outcomes

inquiries; hence, embracing and leveraging new and emerging technologies emerging technologies is essential in the fight against cybercrime in the Philippines.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed ethical guidelines throughout the research process. Approval was obtained from relevant institutional review boards and the selected Philippine National Police Anti-Cybercrime Units to ensure all research activities were conducted within legal and ethical boundaries. Informed consent was gathered from all participants in order to make sure of their awareness and voluntary participation. Data privacy and confidentiality were strictly upheld, with participant information anonymized and securely stored. Moreover, the research adhered to the principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility, ensuring no harm to participants and maintaining the highest standards of ethical conduct.

Acknowledgements

The authors extend their gratitude to all participants from the Philippine National Police Anti-Cybercrime Unit for their valuable contributions and willingness to participate in this study. We also thank the College of Criminal Justice Education at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas for their support and assistance throughout the research process. Special thanks are directed to our thesis adviser for their guidance, insights, and constructive feedback, which greatly enhanced the quality of this work. Lastly, we appreciate the patience and encouragement of our families and peers, whose support was indispensable in the completion of this study.

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